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Enhancing the
Scuba Diving
Experience

Enhancing the SCUBA DIVING experience

This research forms part of the Green Bubbles RISE Project

Green Bubbles

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1. Introduction and method of research

The purpose of this research was to determine divers' experience versus expectations regarding the diving experience in general. The results can assist to design strategies to manage dive destinations as well as the experience based on the needs of the market. In essence, the purpose of this research was to provide direction on how to enhance the scuba diving experience. To achieve this aim, an online questionnaire was designed using Google Forms. The questionnaire consisted of six sections:

- 📄 Section A measured divers' socio-demographic profile.
- 📄 Section B measured divers' economic profile regarding their annual spending.
- 📄 Section C measured divers' diving preferences, certifications and level of experience.
- 📄 Section D measured the primary motives for diving.
- 📄 Section E measured divers' expectations regarding the dive experience related to the experience, destination, the dive site and dive operator.
- 📄 Section F measured divers' experience (satisfaction) regarding the dive destination, dive site and dive operator concerning the destination they last dived at.

The link to the questionnaire was distributed with the assistance of key researchers part of the Green Bubbles RISE project as well as operators located in the case study of Portofino. To increase the number of South African respondents, DANSA assisted in disseminating the questionnaire. The survey ran from February 2016 until September 2017. It was a complicated process to encourage divers to complete the questionnaire. After multiple attempts to increase the number of respondents, a total of 198 completed questionnaire could be obtained. The data was exported to Microsoft® Excel® for basic data analysis, where after SPSS Version 24 (2017) was used to analyse the data further. Descriptive statistics were used to present the results.

The results will consequently be discussed in three sections. Firstly, the results obtained in the global survey will be presented. Secondly, the respondents who indicated that they dived in the case study of Portofino were extracted to provide a case study perspective on divers' needs. Finally, the results obtained in a separate survey conducted in Ponta do Ouro are also discussed. This was done to compare the results obtained in both case studies as well as globally and to make recommendations on how to enhance the scuba diving experience.

This research forms part of the Green Bubbles Rise Project. The Green Bubbles project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 643712. Please note that this report reflects only the researchers' views. The Research Executive Agency is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

2. Study results

2.1 Section A: Global perspective

2.1.1 Gender

The majority of respondents were male (68%), and 32% were female.

GENDER	2017
Male	68%
Female	32%

2.1.2 Home language

Respondents were mainly Italian speaking (82%), followed by 10% who were English speaking and 3% who spoke Afrikaans (an official language in South Africa). German-speaking respondents accounted for 2% of the respondents, while 3% spoke other languages, which included Spanish, French and Greek.

LANGUAGE	%
Italian	72%
English	10%
Afrikaans	3%
German	2%
Other	3%

2.1.3 Average age

The largest group of respondents were in the 45 to 54 years (30%) age category, followed by respondents in the 35 to 44 years category (24%). The average age of respondents who participated in the survey was 45 years old.

AGE CATEGORY	%
<24 years	3%
25-34 years	16%
35-44 years	24%
45-54 years	30%
55-64 years	19%
65+ years	4%
AVERAGE AGE	45 years

2.1.4 Marital status

The majority of the respondents were married (49%), followed by 28% who were single, and 14% who live together (cohabitant). Four percent (4%) of the respondents were divorced, 3% were separated, and 2% were in a relationship.

MARITAL STATUS	%
Married	49%
Single	28%
In a relationship	2%
Divorced	4%
Cohabitant	14%
Separated	3%

2.1.5 Country of origin

Respondents indicated that their country of origin was Italy (80%), followed by 7% who originated from South Africa, and 7% were from other countries, which included Germany, France and Sardinia. Three percent (3%) originated from the UK, while 1% respectively indicated that their countries of origin were Spain, Switzerland or the USA.

COUNTRY	%
Italy	80%
South Africa	7%
Spain	1%
Switzerland	1%
UK	3%
USA	1%
Other	7%

2.1.6 Annual spending on diving activities (currency Euro)

Respondents indicated that they spend on average €3115 on diving and related activities per year. The highest spending categories were on transport to dive sites/destinations, followed by spending on scuba dives, accommodation, food and beverages, dive courses and additional training.

SPENDING CATEGORY	AMOUNT IN €
Scuba dives (i.e. only the dive, plus boat lift, tanks, and weight if applicable)	847.27
Dive courses and additional training	205.38
Transport to dive sites/destinations (e.g. by car, plane, etc.)	874.60
Accommodation (during your dive trips)	618.58
Visa(s) (if applicable for your dive trips)	34.72
Hiring scuba diving equipment/gear	32.15
Food and beverages (during your dive trips)	267.02
Other activities at dive site/destination, e.g. snorkeling	44.39
Dive insurance and, if applicable, renewal of dive credentials (e.g. teaching status)	126.51
Other expenses not listed	64.74
Average total spending per annum	3115.36

2.1.7 Average nights in a diving destination

On average, divers stay at least five nights in a diving destination. Eighteen percent (18%) indicated that they usually spend seven nights in a destination, followed by 17% who indicated that they usually do not overnight where they dive. Fifteen percent (15%) indicated that they stay two nights at the destination where they dive, while 12% stay for at least two nights.

NIGHTS	%
0 nights	17%
1 night	15%
2 nights	12%
3 nights	7%
4 nights	3%
5 nights	8%
6 nights	4%
7 nights	18%

8 nights	1%
10 nights	6%
11+ nights	9%
AVERAGE	4.95 Nights

2.1.8 Average number of people during diving trips

Respondents indicated that they usually travel with one additional person (33%) or two persons (22%). Nine percent (9%) indicated that they travel alone, followed by 7% who travel in groups of 11 or more people. On average, divers travel in groups of four people.

GROUP SIZE	%
None	9%
1 person	33%
2 persons	22%
3 persons	6%
4 persons	6%
5 persons	5%
6 persons	5%
8 persons	5%
10 persons	2%
11+ persons	7%
AVERAGE	3.61 People

2.1.9 Preferred discipline of recreational diving

Regarding the preferred discipline of recreational diving, respondents indicated that they prefer the following: just dive (99%), night dives (94%), wreck diving (90%), nitrox diving, and underwater photography/video (82%, respectively).

RECREATIONAL DIVING	YES	NO
Cave diving	57%	43%
Wreck diving	90%	10%
Ice diving	27%	73%
Deep diving	60%	40%
Altitude diving	30%	70%
Dry suit	61%	39%
Drift diving	71%	29%
Free diving	39%	61%
Night diving	94%	6%
Nitrox diving	82%	18%
Underwater navigation	49%	51%
Underwater photography/video	82%	18%
Underwater search and recovery	47%	53%
Side mount diving	21%	79%
Rebreather	18%	82%
Underwater archaeology	62%	38%
Trimix diving	26%	74%
Just dive	99%	1%
Other	31%	69%

2.1.10 Preferred place to dive

Seas and oceans (99%) are the most preferred place to dive. This was followed by lakes (51%), caves (48%), rivers (26%) and quarries (26%).

PLACE	YES	NO
Seas and oceans	99%	1%
Lakes	51%	49%
Caves	48%	52%
Rivers	30%	70%
Quarries	26%	74%
Other	5%	95%

2.1.11 Usual dive place

Respondents indicated that they usually dive in seas and oceans (99%), followed by lakes (46%), caves (24%) and quarries (22%).

PLACE	YES	NO
Seas and oceans	99%	1%
Lakes	46%	54%
Caves	24%	76%
Rivers	15%	85%
Quarries	22%	78%
Other	3%	97%

2.1.12 Number of years diving

Forty-eight percent (48%) of the respondents indicated that they have between one and 10 years' diving experience, followed by 29% who indicated 11 to 20 years of experience. Sixteen percent (16%) had between 21 and 30 years' experience. On average, respondents had been diving for 14 years.

YEARS DIVING	%
1-10 years	48%
11-20 years	29%
21-30 years	16%
31-40 years	5%
41+ years	2%
AVERAGE	14.12 Years

2.1.13 Number of dives logged

Twenty-two percent (22%) of respondents indicated that they have already logged between 201 and 500 dives, followed by those who have logged more than 900 dives (21%). On average, respondents have already logged 976 dives.

DIVES	%
1-50 dives	18%
51-100 dives	12%
100-200 dives	16%
201-500 dives	22%
501-900 dives	11%
901+ dives	21%
AVERAGE	975.99 dives logged

2.1.14 Number of dives logged per year

On average, respondents log 269 dives per year. Most of the respondents log between 21 and 50 dives per year (33%), followed by those who log between 1 and 10 dives (24%) and 11 and 20 dives per year.

DIVES	%
1-10 dives	24%
11-20 dives	18%
21-50 dives	33%
51-100 dives	13%
100+ dives	12%
AVERAGE	268.97 dives per year

2.1.15 Level and average number of certifications

On average, respondents indicated that they have three speciality certifications, followed by basic (2.94), pro (1.97), dry (1.24) and technical (0.87). The certifying agencies that issued most of their certifications were PADI, SSI, FIPSAS, CMAS and FIAS.

LEVEL AND AVERAGE NUMBER OF CERTIFICATIONS HELD IN EACH LEVEL	
Basic (open, advanced, rescue)	2.94
Pro (Dive Master, Assistant Instructor/Instructor of any level and speciality)	1.97
Speciality (including caves/caverns, ice, recreational Nitrox, but excluding all those under "technical" and "dry" categories below)	3.29
Technical (all types/levels for Trimix, Rebreather, Side Mount, Deco Dive, DPV, etc.)	0.87
Dry (Oxygen provider, Gas blender, Equipment Specialist, First Aid, Boat operator, etc.)	1.24
Certifying company that issued most certifications	PADI, SSI, FIPSAS, CMAS, FIAS

2.1.16 Frequencies of diving

Respondents indicated that they dive both on holidays and on weekends (62%), followed by during most of the year (22%), while 16% indicated that they only dive during holidays.

FREQUENCY	%
Only when I am on holidays	16%
During most of the year, e.g. on weekends	22%
Both on holidays and in the weekend	62%

2.1.17 Frequency of diving in the salt-water areas

Regarding the frequency of diving in salt-water areas, respondents had to indicate on a five-point Likert scale (1 = Never and 5 = Always) how often they dive in salt-water areas. Respondents indicated that they often dive in the Mediterranean and the Black Sea, while they sometimes dive in the Red Sea.

SALT-WATER AREAS	RATING OUT OF 5	FREQUENCY
a. Mediterranean and the Black Sea	3.88	often
b. North and Baltic Sea	1.11	Never
c. Arctic and Antarctic	1.03	Never
d. Indian Ocean	2.30	Rarely
e. Atlantic Ocean	1.66	Rarely
f. Pacific Ocean	1.64	Rarely

g. Caribbean Sea	1.82	Rarely
h. Red Sea	2.65	Sometimes
i. Other	1.59	Rarely

2.1.18 Main motives for diving

Respondents indicated that their primary motives for diving were because they regard themselves as a scuba diving enthusiast, because scuba diving is a fun activity, because they want to experience peace and tranquillity, because they want to learn about marine wildlife, and because scuba diving contributes towards their overall well-being. To form part of an expedition and the element of risk and surprise associated with scuba diving motivate divers to a lesser extent.

MOTIVES FOR DIVING	AVERAGE OUT OF 5	LEVEL OF AGREEMENT
I am a scuba diving enthusiast	4.46	Strongly agree
Scuba diving is a fun activity	4.43	Strongly agree
To experience peace and tranquillity	4.35	Strongly agree
To learn about marine wildlife	4.32	Strongly agree
Scuba diving contributes towards my overall happiness and quality of life	4.24	Strongly agree
To gain experiences I can look back on	4.01	Agree
To explore new destinations	3.96	Agree
Scuba diving is part of my lifestyle	3.92	Agree
To search for specific species	3.90	Agree
Out of curiosity	3.89	Agree
For new experiences – Scuba diving is something I have always wanted to do	3.82	Agree
To acquire new skills	3.76	Agree
To photograph marine life	3.65	Agree
To spend time with family and friends	3.45	Agree
It is challenging/adventurous	3.41	Agree
Scuba diving allows me to escape from reality (transports me to another world)	3.35	Agree
To escape from daily routine	3.05	Neutral
To collect data that can support science	3.03	Neutral
To be part of an expedition	2.71	Disagree
The element of risk and surprise associated with scuba diving	2.22	Disagree

2.1.19 Location diving at the most

Respondents indicated the following locations where they dive at the most:

- 📍 Portofino, Italy
- 📍 Santa Margherita, Italy
- 📍 Sodwana Bay, South Africa
- 📍 Chioggia, Italy
- 📍 Sardinia
- 📍 Sicily
- 📍 Lake Lugano, Switzerland

2.1.20 Aspects necessary for a memorable diving experience

In this part of the questionnaire, respondents had to indicate their expectations regarding the dive destination, the dive site, and dive operators, i.e. they had to indicate the aspects they regard as essential and expect for a quality and satisfactory experience. This experience is referred to as a memorable experience i.e. one that is not only remembered but also treasured. Respondents then had to indicate the destination where they dive at the most and evaluate the same set of aspects based on their experience. With this information, a gap analysis could be done to indicate whether divers' expectations were exceeded or not. Divers' expectations were measured on a five-point Likert scale of importance, while their experience was rated on a five-point Likert scale of satisfaction. The following tables show the mean values (average out of 5) for both their expectations and satisfaction with the experience, while the 'Difference' column indicates whether their expectations were met or whether they were dissatisfied.

Regarding the aspects divers regarded as necessary about the **dive destination**, certain aspects exceeded divers' expectations, especially quality shopping, the variety of restaurants, the variety of tourist attractions in the area as well as the quality of the food available in the areas. The variety of accommodation options available at dive destinations as well as the variety of things to do and see when diving, the adequate number of dive operators to choose from, friendly and accepting community and safe and secure environment also exceeded respondents' expectations. However, while the following aspects were rated as very important for a satisfactory and memorable overall diving experience at the dive destination, divers were dissatisfied with the following: wildlife/natural setting, easily accessible (i.e. to reach by car/plane) and especially with affordable prices at local businesses and restaurants, overall fair prices asked at the destination and affordable accommodation.

Expectations versus experience regarding the dive destination

ASPECTS PERTAINING TO THE DIVE DESTINATION	EXPECTATIONS	EXPERIENCE	DIFFERENCE
Quality shopping	2.18	3.04	0.85
Variety of restaurants	3.05	3.76	0.71
Variety of tourist attractions in the area	3.06	3.67	0.60
Quality food (in restaurants, markets, shops, etc.)	3.29	3.86	0.57
Variety of accommodation options available	3.49	3.71	0.22
Variety of things to do and see when I am not diving	3.44	3.64	0.19
Adequate number of dive operators to choose from	3.64	3.77	0.13
Friendly and accepting community	3.84	3.94	0.10
Safe and secure environment	4.26	4.27	0.01
Wildlife/natural setting	4.29	4.27	-0.02
Easily accessible (i.e. to reach by car/plane)	3.93	3.90	-0.03
Affordable prices at local businesses and restaurants	3.84	3.63	-0.21
Overall fair prices asked at destination	4.30	4.07	-0.23
Affordable accommodation	4.03	3.78	-0.25

Regarding the aspects pertaining to the **dive site**, respondents had high expectations regarding underwater visibility, topography of the site (e.g. coral reefs, underwater cliffs, rock reefs, caves, etc.), wildlife/marine life at the site, seeing endangered and rare species, and the historical and cultural items (e.g. shipwrecks, artifacts, statues). Then again, as seen in the 'Difference' column, these expectations were not met, which indicates room for improvement to meet divers'

expectations. On the other hand, divers had lower expectations regarding underwater photography/video opportunities, reputation as a must-do dive site, the absence of strong current, good accessibility to the site, good year-round climate, and favourable water temperature. These expectations were, however, exceeded, and dive destinations should emphasise these in marketing campaigns.

Expectations versus experience regarding the dive site

ASPECTS PERTAINING TO THE DIVE SITE	EXPECTATIONS	EXPERIENCE	DIFFERENCE
Underwater photography/video opportunities	3.52	4.16	0.64
Reputation as a must-do dive site	3.25	3.84	0.59
Absence of strong current	3.34	3.75	0.41
Good accessibility to the site	3.70	4.08	0.38
Good year-round climate	3.28	3.51	0.23
Favourable water temperature	3.60	3.76	0.16
Underwater visibility	4.02	3.87	-0.14
Topography of the site (e.g. coral reefs, underwater cliffs, rock reefs, caves, etc.)	4.45	4.18	-0.27
Wildlife/marine life at the site	4.53	4.24	-0.28
Seeing endangered and rare species	3.62	3.31	-0.31
Historical and cultural items (e.g. shipwrecks, artefacts, statues)	3.95	3.51	-0.44

Regarding the aspects divers regarded as important to the **dive operators**, again certain expectations were exceeded, while divers were dissatisfied with others. Divers were mainly satisfied with the following aspects pertaining to the dive operators:

Expectations versus experience regarding the dive operators: aspects satisfied with

ASPECTS PERTAINING TO THE DIVE OPERATORS	EXPECTATIONS	EXPERIENCE	DIFFERENCE
Affiliation to a specific certification agency	2.81	3.77	0.96
Opportunity to hire equipment / gear	3.64	4.21	0.57
Well-marketed on various platforms, i.e. information is easily accessible	3.12	3.58	0.46
Equipped for junior divers	3.39	3.74	0.35
Catering to different dive levels	4.08	4.36	0.28
Credible reputation	4.03	4.23	0.21
Flexible dive times (e.g. allowed to dive longer than scheduled)	3.86	4.04	0.18
Dive shop and/or equipment maintenance services available	3.44	3.61	0.17
Offering other products and activities	3.58	3.74	0.16
Strict enforcement of diving rules	3.99	4.13	0.13
Friendly and well-trained dive instructors and operators	4.40	4.47	0.06
Easy to access/reach	3.85	3.89	0.03
Full-days available	3.78	3.80	0.02
Possibility to buy a "Dive & Stay package" (dive and accommodation)	3.54	3.54	0.00

The following aspects, however, did not meet divers' expectations.

Expectations versus experience regarding the dive operators: aspects dissatisfied with

ASPECTS PERTAINING TO THE DIVE OPERATORS	EXPECTATIONS	EXPERIENCE	DIFFERENCE
Being able to deal with emergencies	4.68	4.32	-0.36
Uncrowded experiences (restricted number of divers at the dive site)	4.30	3.97	-0.33
Parking available at the operators or at a discount price	3.74	3.47	-0.27
Well-maintained gear and equipment	4.37	4.10	-0.27
Ensuring the safety of the divers at all times	4.61	4.38	-0.23
Equipped for physically challenged divers	3.52	3.32	-0.21
Thorough safety briefings and checks	4.39	4.18	-0.20
Fair prices asked (value-for-money)	4.18	4.01	-0.18
Freedom to explore and learn while diving	4.22	4.07	-0.15
Well-maintained facilities	4.28	4.17	-0.11
Informative briefings on environmental aspects	4.23	4.13	-0.10
Delivering good quality service	4.34	4.25	-0.09
Spacious charters	3.85	3.81	-0.04
Informing divers of what to expect	4.21	4.18	-0.03

2.2 Section B: Portofino, Italy

2.2.1 Profile of Portofino divers

Divers, who indicated that the case study area of Portofino was the destination where they dive at the most, were extracted from the online survey data to provide an overview of what these divers expect regarding the dive experience at the destination. This resulted in 87 respondents who were analysed separately. The table below summarises the profile of these divers. The majority of respondents to Portofino were male, married, Italian divers, with an average age of 46 years. On average, they spent five nights in the area and travel with four persons. Their preferred recreational diving disciplines were just dive, followed by free diving, wreck diving, nitrox diving and underwater video/photography. They prefer to dive in seas and oceans as well as lakes and caves, and these are also the places where they usually dive. On average, these divers have been diving for 13 years, have logged over 500 dives and log an average of 33 dives per year, which they do during their holidays or over weekends. Divers dive most frequently in the Mediterranean and the Black Sea. The majority of their certifications are either basic or speciality with PADI being the certifying agency issuing most of their certifications. Their main motives for diving include: I am a scuba diving enthusiast, scuba diving is a fun activity, to experience peace and tranquillity, to learn about marine wildlife and scuba diving contributes towards my overall happiness and quality of life. On average, divers annually spend €2777.71 on recreational diving, of which they spend the most on transport, followed by scuba dives, accommodation, food and beverages, and diving courses and additional training.

Profile of the respondents

PROFILE FACTORS	RESULTS
Gender	78% Male; 21% Female
Language	99% Italian; 1% German
Age	Average = 46 years
Marital status	41% Married; 25% Single; 16% Cohabitant
Country of origin	99% Italy; 1% Switzerland
Average number of nights spent at diving destination	Average = 5 nights
Average number of people in travel group during diving trip	Average group size = 3.95 persons
Preferred discipline of recreational diving	97% Just dive; 96% Free diving; 94% Wreck diving; 83% Nitrox diving; 81% Underwater video/photography; 66% Dry suit; 66% Drift diving; 63% Trimix diving; 60% Cave diving; 54% Deep diving; 48% Dry suit
Preferred diving place	99% Seas and oceans; 49% Lakes; 47% Caves; 30% Rivers; 23% Quarries
Usual place to dive	99% Seas and oceans; 41% Lakes; 25% Caves; 16% Rivers; 13% Quarries
Average number of years diving	Average = 13 years
Average number of dives logged	Average = 502 dives
Average number of dives logged per year	Average = 33 dives
Level and average number of certifications held in each level	
Basic (Open, Advanced, Rescue)	3
Pro (Dive Master, Assistant Instructor/Instructor of any level and speciality)	2

Speciality (including caves/caverns, ice, recreational Nitrox, but excluding all those under "technical" and "dry" categories below)	3
Technical (all types/levels for Trimix, Rebreather, Side Mount, Deco Dive, DPV, etc.)	1
Dry (Oxygen provider, Gas blender, Equipment Specialist, First Aid, Boat operator, etc.)	1
Certifying company that issued most certifications	PADI, SSI, FIPSAS, CMAS, FIAS
Dive regularity	11% Only when on holiday 22% During most of the year, e.g. weekends 67% Both on holiday and over the weekends

Frequency of dives in salt water areas (average out of 5 to be interpreted on the original Likert scale where 1 = never and 5 = always)

Mediterranean and the Black Sea	4.21 Often to always
North and Baltic Sea	1.08 Never
Arctic and Antarctic	1.03 Never
Indian Ocean	2.07 Rarely
Atlantic Ocean	1.45 Never to rarely
Pacific Ocean	1.58 Never to rarely
Caribbean Sea	1.68 Never to rarely
Red Sea	2.70 Rarely to sometimes

Main motives to dive (average out of 5 to be interpreted on the original Likert scale where 1 = Strongly disagree and 5 = Strongly agree)

I am a scuba diving enthusiast	4.55 Strongly agree
Scuba diving is a fun activity	4.51 Strongly agree
To experience peace and tranquillity	4.45 Agree
To learn about marine wildlife	4.41 Agree
Scuba diving contributes towards my overall happiness and quality of life	4.33 Agree
To gain experiences I can look back on	4.05 Agree
To search for specific species	4.04 Agree
To explore new destinations	4.01 Agree
To acquire new skills	3.96 Agree
Out of curiosity	3.93 Agree
For new experiences – Scuba diving is something I have always wanted to do	3.89 Agree
Scuba diving is part of my lifestyle	3.88 Agree
To photograph marine life	3.73 Agree
To spend time with family and friends	3.61 Agree
It is challenging/adventurous	3.46 Neutral
Scuba diving allows me to escape from reality (transports me to another world)	3.34 Neutral
To collect data that can support science	3.07 Neutral
To escape from daily routine	2.96 Neutral to disagree
To be part of an expedition	2.67 Neutral to disagree
The element of risk and surprise associated with scuba diving	2.18 Disagree

Average spending per category per year (Euro)

a. Scuba dives (i.e. only the dive, plus boat lift, tanks, and weight if applicable)	708.39
b. Dive courses and additional training	215.98
c. Transport to dive sites/destinations (e.g. by car, plane, etc.)	869.31
d. Accommodation (during your dive trips)	498.28
e. Visa(s) (if applicable for your dive trips)	16.32
f. Hiring scuba diving equipment/gear	24.88
g. Food and beverages (during your dive trips)	259.08
h. Other activities at dive site/destination, e.g. snorkeling	17.48
i. Dive insurance and, if applicable, renewal of dive credentials (e.g. teaching status)	89.71
j. Other expenses not listed	78.28
Average total spending	2777.71

2.2.2 Creating a memorable diving experience in Portofino

Respondents who dived in Portofino indicated that they dived mostly with the following dive centres: Bubble Lounge Diving in Recco, Dive Passion, Diving Evolution, Marina Diving, San Fruttuosa Diving, Tortuga Diving and Marina Diving. The following three tables indicate Portofino divers' expectations regarding the dive destination, the dive site, and the dive operators.

In terms of the aspects divers regarded as important pertaining to the **dive destination**; while the following aspects were rated as very important for a satisfactory and memorable overall diving experience, divers were left dissatisfied after their dive: friendly and accepting community, easily accessible (i.e. to reach by car/plane), overall fair prices asked at destination, affordable prices at local businesses and restaurants and affordable accommodation. Other aspects, however, exceeded their expectations, especially quality shopping, the variety of restaurants, the variety of tourist attractions in the area as well as the quality of the food available in the area. The variety of things to do and see when I am not diving, the adequate number of dive operators to choose from, the variety of accommodation options available, the wildlife/natural setting and the safe and secure environment also exceeded divers' expectations.

Expectations versus experience regarding the dive destination

ASPECTS ABOUT THE DIVE DESTINATION	EXPECTATIONS	EXPERIENCE	DIFFERENCE
Quality shopping	2.27	3.28	1.02
Variety of restaurants	3.11	3.88	0.77
Variety of tourist attractions in the area	3.18	3.75	0.57
Quality food (in restaurants, markets, shops, etc.)	3.32	3.89	0.57
Variety of things to do and see when I am not diving	3.58	3.77	0.20
Adequate number of dive operators to choose from	3.66	3.84	0.18
Variety of accommodation options available	3.58	3.70	0.12
Wildlife/natural setting	4.33	4.40	0.07
Safe and secure environment	4.25	4.32	0.07
Friendly and accepting community	3.76	3.70	-0.06
Easily accessible (i.e. to reach by car/plane)	3.95	3.88	-0.07
Overall fair prices asked at destination	4.31	4.09	-0.22

Affordable prices at local businesses and restaurants	3.79	3.53	-0.26
Affordable accommodation	4.02	3.63	-0.39

Regarding the aspects pertaining to the **dive site**, respondents had high expectations regarding wildlife/marine life at the site, underwater visibility, topography of the site (e.g. coral reefs, underwater cliffs, rock reefs, caves, etc.), historical and cultural items (e.g. shipwrecks, artifacts, statues) and seeing endangered and rare species. However, as seen in the 'Difference' column, these expectations were not met, which indicates room for improvement to meet divers' expectations. On the other hand, divers had lower expectations regarding underwater photography/video opportunities, Portofino's reputation as a must-do dive site, and absence of strong current, good accessibility to the site, favourable water temperature and good year-round climate. These expectations were, however, exceeded, which Portofino as a diving destination can use to its advantage.

Expectations versus experience regarding the dive site

ASPECTS PERTAINING TO THE DIVE SITE	EXPECTATIONS	EXPERIENCE	DIFFERENCE
Underwater photography/video opportunities	3.52	4.21	0.69
Reputation as a must-do dive site	3.31	3.89	0.58
Absence of strong current	3.38	3.85	0.47
Good accessibility to the site	3.77	4.10	0.33
Favourable water temperature	3.56	3.74	0.17
Good year-round climate	3.37	3.49	0.12
Wildlife/marine life at the site	4.53	4.39	-0.14
Underwater visibility	4.02	3.88	-0.14
Topography of the site (e.g. coral reefs, underwater cliffs, rock reefs, caves, etc.)	4.46	4.23	-0.23
Historical and cultural items (e.g. shipwrecks, artefacts, statues)	4.05	3.65	-0.40
Seeing endangered and rare species	3.70	3.29	-0.41

Concerning the aspects that divers regarded as important to the **dive operators**, again certain expectations were exceeded, while divers were dissatisfied with others. Alarmingly, more aspects disappointed the divers compared to those that exceeded their expectations. Divers were mainly satisfied with the dive operators' affiliation to a specific certification agency, the fact that operators are well marketed on various platforms, i.e. information is easily accessible, the opportunities to hire equipment/gear, the flexible dive times (e.g. allowed to dive longer than scheduled) and because dive operators can cater to different dive levels. The following aspects, however, disappointed divers: informing divers of what to expect, well-maintained facilities, delivering good quality service, possibility to buy a "Dive & Stay package" (dive and accommodation), ensuring the safety of the divers at all times, fair prices asked (value-for-money), informative briefings on environmental aspects, easy to access/reach, well-maintained gear and equipment, freedom to explore and learn while diving, being able to deal with emergencies, equipped for physically challenged divers, uncrowded experiences (restricted number of divers at the dive site), thorough safety briefings and checks, and parking available at the operator's or a discount price.

Expectations versus experience regarding the dive operators

ASPECTS PERTAINING TO THE DIVE OPERATORS	EXPECTATIONS	EXPERIENCE	DIFFERENCE
Affiliation to a specific certification agency	2.88	3.67	0.79
Well-marketed on various platforms, i.e. information is easily accessible	3.04	3.56	0.53
Opportunity to hire equipment / gear	3.74	4.23	0.48
Flexible dive times (e.g. allowed to dive longer than scheduled)	3.86	4.07	0.21
Catering to different dive levels	4.11	4.31	0.20
Credible reputation	3.98	4.15	0.17
Dive shop and/or equipment maintenance services available	3.48	3.63	0.14
Friendly and well-trained dive instructors and operators	4.33	4.46	0.14
Full-days available	3.78	3.89	0.11
Offering other products and activities	3.77	3.85	0.09
Equipped for junior divers	3.65	3.70	0.05
Strict enforcement of diving rules	4.06	4.10	0.04
Spacious charters	3.81	3.84	0.03
Informing divers of what to expect	4.17	4.14	-0.03
Well-maintained facilities	4.20	4.16	-0.04
Delivering good quality service	4.38	4.26	-0.11
Possibility to buy a "Dive & Stay package" (dive and accommodation)	3.52	3.39	-0.13
Ensuring the safety of the divers at all times	4.57	4.41	-0.16
Fair prices asked (value-for-money)	4.17	4.00	-0.17
Informative briefings on environmental aspects	4.21	4.01	-0.20
Easy to access/reach	4.00	3.78	-0.22
Well-maintained gear and equipment	4.36	4.14	-0.23
Freedom to explore and learn while diving	4.23	3.98	-0.25
Being able to deal with emergencies	4.66	4.36	-0.30
Equipped for physically challenged divers	3.80	3.45	-0.34
Uncrowded experiences (restricted number of divers at the dive site)	4.27	3.91	-0.36
Thorough safety briefings and checks	4.42	4.06	-0.36
Parking available at the operator's or a discount price	3.99	3.42	-0.57

2.3 Section C: Ponta do Ouro, Mozambique

2.3.1 Method of research

Data were gathered between 3 April 2017 and 7 April 2017 in Ponta do Ouro, Mozambique. Unfortunately, due to the limited space available in the questionnaire, only divers' expectations could be measured. Therefore, for this case study, divers' satisfaction with the dive experience could not be included, and only the aspects that divers regard as important for a satisfying diving experience were measured. The questionnaires were distributed to divers at five different dive operators: Back to Basics Adventures, Gozo Azul Diving, Oceana Diving, Adventures, and Devocean. The aim was to get a minimum of 300 questionnaires; however, only 145 completed questionnaires were administered. The author acknowledges the limitation of an unrepresentative sample; however, since this is exploratory research, the results are nevertheless considered relevant and significant to consider. In this regard, it is important to note that the research at Ponta do Ouro will continue in 2018 to obtain a valid sample. The questionnaire used to survey divers at Ponta do Ouro comprised four sections. Only Sections B, C, and D were used for this research.

- Section B measured the socio-demographic profile and consisted of gender, home language, marital status, occupation, how many return visits, and diving qualification, among others.
- Section C captured the spending behaviours of the divers that consisted of scuba dives, dive courses, accommodation, and transportation, to name but a few.
- Section D measured the scuba diving expectations of the respondents with regard to the dive experience, the dive sites and lastly the dive operators. The section on memorable experience measured 53 items on a five-point Likert scale and respondents were asked to indicate how important they considered each item (1 = not important; 2 = less important; 3 = important; 4 = very important and 5 = extremely important). Up to date, there have been no studies that have determined the critical success factors that contribute to a memorable diving experience. However, the statements related to general management, marketing, and human resources were based on and adapted from previous studies that applied this research to other sectors in the tourism industry.

Microsoft© Excel© was used for data capturing and basic data analysis, where after SPSS Version 24 (2017) was used to analyse the data further. Descriptive statistics were also performed to present the results. The results will consequently be discussed.

2.3.2 Profile of respondents

The table summarises the main findings regarding the profile of the surveyed respondents at Ponta do Ouro in 2017. Divers to Ponta do Ouro during the survey period were mainly English speaking, married males with a degree, with an average age of 38 years and travelling from South Africa. During their stay, they spent an average of R11 611.29 (€684). They were furthermore first-time visitors who spent an average of seven nights in the area with seven years of diving experience, and they prefer reef diving. They indicated an open water diving certificate as their level of certification with over 300 dives logged and have an average of 29 dives per year. It was found that gender, age, and level of education are consistent with the majority of previous research that was conducted on scuba divers, while marital status contradicts the majority of the previous research. This finding emphasises that scuba divers cannot be regarded as homogenous regarding their socio-demographic characteristics.

Profile of the respondents

PROFILE FACTORS	RESULTS
Gender	65% Male; 35% Female
Language	59% English; 29% Afrikaans
Age	Average = 38 years
Level of education	40% Degree
Marital status	46% Married; 45% Single
Country of origin	78% South Africa
Nights in area	Average = 6,57 nights
First visit	53% Yes; 47% No
Years diving	Average = 7.06 years
Type of diving	16% Reef diving; 14% Open water; 11% Wreck diving
Dives logged	Average = 302.58 dives
Number of dives per year	Average = 28,67 dives
Preferred type of diving	16% Reef diving; 14% Open water; 11% Wreck diving
Level of certification	29% Open water; 25% Advanced
Average total spending	R11 611,29 (€684)

2.3.3 Creating a memorable diving experience in Ponta do Ouro

Similar to the online survey, three aspects of the dive experience were measured: aspects regarding the dive itself, the dive site and the operator. The following section discusses the results obtained for these three aspects. A mean value (an average out of 5 based on the original Likert scale of importance) was calculated for each statement to ease the discussion. Please note that only the top 5 aspects will be discussed as well as the lesser essential aspects as indicated by the respondents.

Respondents indicated that the following aspects are vital for a memorable dive experience: friendly and accepting community, safe and secure environment, overall fair prices asked at the destination, quality food and wildlife, and natural setting. The aspects that were regarded as less important were quality shopping opportunities, and variety of tourist attractions in the area, easily accessible, a variety of restaurants and the variety of things to do and see when I am not diving. However, when interpreted on the original Likert scale, these aspects were still rated as important, but less important when compared to the top 5 aspects.

Memorable experience aspects regarding the dive destination

DIVE EXPERIENCE FEATURES/ASPECTS	NOT IMPORTANT	UNIMPORTANT	NEUTRAL	IMPORTANT	EXTREMELY IMPORTANT	AVERAGE OUT OF 5
Friendly and accepting community	0%	1%	21%	42%	36%	4.21
Safe and secure environment	0%	3%	18%	34%	45%	4.21
Overall fair prices asked at destination	0%	2%	20%	50%	28%	4.04
Quality food	0%	4%	22%	46%	28%	3.98
Wildlife/natural setting	1%	5%	24%	43%	27%	3.91
Affordable accommodation	0%	6%	21%	54%	19%	3.86

Variety of accommodation options available	0%	4%	26%	50%	20%	3.85
Affordable prices at local business & restaurants	0%	4%	28%	52%	16%	3.81
Adequate number of dive operators to choose from	1%	6%	26%	49%	18%	3.77
Variety of thing to do & see when I am not diving	3%	4%	33%	40%	20%	3.71
Variety of restaurants	0%	6%	36%	40%	18%	3.70
Easily accessible	1%	7%	33%	43%	16%	3.67
Variety of tourist attractions in the area	0%	9%	33%	42%	16%	3.65
Quality shopping opportunities	6%	16%	32%	30%	16%	3.34

Regarding the memorable experience aspects important at dive sites, respondents indicated that the following aspects were the most important:

- Wildlife/marine life at the site
- Underwater visibility
- Topography of the site
- Seeing endangered and rare species
- Favourable water temperature

The aspects that were regarded as less important to the respondents included:

- Historical and cultural items
- Underwater photography/video opportunities
- Absence of strong current
- Good year-round climate
- Reputation as must-do dive site

Memorable experience aspects regarding the dive sites

DIVE SITE FEATURES/ASPECTS	NOT IMPORTANT	UNIMPORTANT	NEUTRAL	IMPORTANT	EXTREMELY IMPORTANT	AVERAGE OUT OF 5
Wildlife/marine life at the site	0%	2%	19%	30%	49%	4.25
Underwater visibility	0%	3%	14%	46%	37%	4.18
Topography of the site	0%	4%	23%	37%	36%	4.05
Seeing endangered and rare species	1%	3%	20%	51%	25%	3.97
Favourable water temperature	0%	4%	26%	43%	27%	3.92
Reputation as must-do dive site	1%	2%	26%	47%	24%	3.90
Good accessibility to the site	1%	4%	27%	45%	23%	3.86
Good year-round climate	1%	5%	25%	48%	21%	3.82
Absence of strong current	2%	4%	33%	40%	21%	3.74
Underwater photography/video opportunities	3%	6%	26%	48%	17%	3.71
Historical and cultural items	2%	5%	33%	41%	19%	3.70

The following table shows the aspects respondents regarded as important when it comes to the specific dive operator they dived with. The top dive operator features were well-maintained gear and equipment, followed by being able to deal with emergencies, friendly and well-trained dive instructors and operators, ensuring the safety of the divers at all times and well-maintained facilities. The aspects deemed less important were parking available at operator or a discount

price, followed by offering other products and activities, information briefings on environmental aspects, full-days available and equipment for physically challenged divers.

Memorable experience aspects regarding the dive operators

DIVE OPERATOR FEATURES	NOT IMPORTANT	UNIMPORTANT	NEUTRAL	IMPORTANT	EXTREMELY IMPORTANT	AVERAGE OUT OF FIVE
Well-maintained gear and equipment	1%	2%	14%	43%	40%	4.20
Being able to deal with emergencies	0%	4%	14%	42%	40%	4.18
Friendly and well-trained dive instructors and operators	0%	3%	14%	47%	36%	4.16
Ensuring the safety of the divers at all times	0%	1%	20%	46%	33%	4.11
Well-maintained facilities	0%	3%	16%	48%	33%	4.10
Fair prices asked	0%	3%	14%	56%	27%	4.07
Delivering good quality service	0%	4%	19%	44%	33%	4.06
Thorough safety briefings and checks	0%	1%	22%	47%	30%	4.05
Strict enforcement of diving rules	0%	2%	22%	44%	32%	4.05
Credible reputation	1%	1%	29%	46%	23%	4.02
Informing divers of what to expect	0%	1%	22%	53%	24%	4.00
Freedom to explore and learn while diving	0%	2%	21%	52%	25%	3.99
Catering to different dive levels	0%	1%	29%	47%	23%	3.92
Possibility to buy a "Dive & Stay package"	2%	7%	15%	48%	28%	3.91
Flexible dive times	2%	3%	20%	54%	21%	3.88
Uncrowded experiences	0%	2%	31%	43%	24%	3.88
Diver shop and/or equipment maintenance services available	2%	4%	26%	41%	27%	3.88
Opportunity to hire equipment / gear	1%	5%	25%	43%	26%	3.86
Well-marked on various platforms	1%	3%	24%	53%	19%	3.85
Easy to access/reach	1%	4%	28%	44%	23%	3.84
Affiliation to a specific certification agency	4%	4%	28%	36%	28%	3.80
Equipped for junior divers	1%	5%	30%	43%	21%	3.79
Spacious charters	1%	7%	26%	46%	20%	3.77
Equipment for physically challenged divers	2%	6%	27%	47%	18%	3.75
Full-days available	1%	5%	32%	43%	19%	3.74
Information briefings on environmental aspects	2%	4%	33%	44%	17%	3.72
Offering other products and activities	3%	7%	27%	47%	16%	3.67
Parking available at the operator's or at a discount price	2%	8%	31%	42%	17%	3.63

3. Recommendations for enhancing the scuba diving experience

Based on the results, the following recommendations are made regarding the dive destination, the dive site and for dive operators to enhance the overall scuba diving experience. Specific strategies are also proposed for the two case study destinations.

3.1 Enhancing the experience at dive destinations

The results of both the global and case study surveys indicated certain aspects that divers regard as important for a satisfying experience with dive destinations.

- ☞ In all three cases, the following aspects exceeded divers' expectations: quality shopping, the variety of restaurants, the variety of tourist attractions in the area as well as the quality of the food available in the area, the variety of things to do and see when not diving, the adequate number of dive operators to choose from, friendly and accepting community, the variety of accommodation options available and safe and secure environment. These aspects should, therefore, be seen as complementary to the diving experience and marketed as auxiliary services and amenities at dive destinations.
- ☞ However, the following aspects left divers disappointed and should be addressed: the wildlife/natural setting, easily accessible (i.e. to reach by car/plane), overall fair prices asked at the destination, affordable prices at local businesses and restaurants and affordable accommodation. In the case of Portofino, compared to the global results, divers were dissatisfied with the aspect friendly and accepting community, while they were satisfied with the wildlife/natural setting of Portofino. The main issues that therefore need to be addressed are regarding accessibility, affordability and community support. The following recommendations are therefore made:
 - Regarding enhancing the accessibility to dive destinations (by car/plane/train), clearer directions and options on how to reach the destinations by various means of transport, including public transport available at the dive destinations, should be available on various platforms, for example destination websites and social media pages.
 - Regarding affordability, it is important to ensure that divers receive a value-for-money experience. While the prices of restaurants and accommodation are mostly out of the dive destinations' control, dive operators should find ways to work together with local businesses to integrate the offerings at the dive destination. This recommendation is dependent on community support, which was another aspect divers indicated as key to their experience. Dive destinations should find ways to offer packages consisting of an all-inclusive scuba diver deal that includes dives, accommodation, discounts at selected restaurants as well as excursions to tourist attractions. This could encourage divers to travel in larger groups, stay longer in the area and as a result spend more, which will lead to a more significant economic impact of recreational diving to the destination. Scuba diver holiday specials and packages could also be a way to increase diver numbers during the off seasons.

3.2 Enhancing the experience at dive sites

- ☞ Divers' expectations were met with regard to the following aspects at the dive sites where they prefer to dive: underwater photography/video opportunities, the dive sites' reputation as a must-do dive site, the absence of

strong current, good accessibility to the site, favourable water temperature and good year-round climate. Again, these aspects should be used to the dive destination as well as dive operators' advantage by emphasising these attributes in marketing campaigns.

- ☛ On the other hand, divers' expectations were not met in terms of the wildlife/marine life at the sites, underwater visibility, topography of the site (e.g. coral reefs, underwater cliffs, rock reefs, caves, etc.), historical and cultural items (e.g. shipwrecks, artifacts, statues) and seeing endangered and rare species. Even though these aspects are mostly out of management's control, there are still certain aspects that can be addressed.
 - There are a few initiatives that Marine Protected Areas (MPAs) and dive operators could consider to preserve the wildlife and marine life at dive sites. For example, the traffic to the dive sites can be managed more carefully to minimise the impact that larger groups of divers can have on the dive site. This implies restricting the number of divers at a time to minimise the environmental impact on the dive site and to ensure that the dive site can be preserved. It is furthermore essential to implement environmental safety briefings before dives to help minimise the impact on the dive sites. This will also educate the divers on the importance of ethical diving practices and the impact that divers can have on the marine ecosystem. Interpretation in the form of informative posters and audio-visual material could also assist in this regard.
 - Underwater visibility was indicated as another critical aspect. Dive destinations should use this feature to its advantage; for example, the coastal waters in Mozambique offer water visibility of up to 40 meters, which is prime visibility for any diver. In Portofino, visibility averages 20 metres/70 feet and can extend to more than 30 metres/100 feet. Destination marketers and dive operators in both case studies can, therefore, use this feature to their advantage by marketing the water visibility of Mozambique.
 - Topography at the sites can also be linked to the wildlife/natural setting. Both case studies offer a unique natural and wildlife setting (fauna and flora). Mozambique, and specifically Ponta do Ouro, has a unique and beautiful natural setting that cannot be found anywhere else in the world. The same goes for Portofino, which is surrounded by steep mountains that plunge straight down to marine canyons resulting in some of the best diving in the Mediterranean. The distinct topography of dive destinations and particularly of the dive sites, therefore, present an opportunity for destination marketers and dive operators to gain a competitive advantage by marketing these features.
 - Historical and cultural items (e.g., shipwrecks, artifacts, statues) were another important aspect to divers. While dive sites such as Portofino offer a variety of historical and cultural items, for example, Christ of the Abyss, as well as a variety of shipwrecks and Ponta do Ouro has similar offerings, divers were not satisfied with this aspect of their experience. This implies that these offerings should be better marketed and packaged.
 - An additional aspect important to divers was seeing endangered and rare species. Ponta do Ouro, for example, offers a variety of rare and endangered species, including whale sharks, manta rays, dugongs, leafy sea dragon, blobfish, sei whale, sperm whale to name but a few. In Portofino hosts a red list species, *Epinephelus marginatus*, the grouper, which is protected in the area as well as *Corallium rubrum* (red coral). The unique species, both the marine as well as the underwater vegetation, should, therefore, be accentuated in the marketing and branding of the case studies as dive destinations.

3.3 Enhancing the experience offered by dive operators

The aspects related to the experience offered by dive operators indicated the most discrepancies and consequently require improvements to enhance divers' experience. The following five key areas of concern were identified that dive operators should take note of to improve divers' experience.

Information and interpretation

- Divers indicated that their expectations were not met regarding informing divers of what to expect, informative briefings on environmental aspects and having the freedom to explore and learn while diving. Dive operators can consider utilising 3D mapping to characterise the dive site. These maps can be shown to divers during briefings to provide them with a better sense of what to expect from their dive. The maps can even be placed on the website or social media pages of the dive operators to give potential divers an idea of the dive experience on offer. Underwater virtual tours and videos of the dive site can also be a way to show the experience. These initiatives can also effectively be used at dive shows and fairs to market the dive site and destination to current and potential divers. Regarding briefings on environmental aspects, dive operators need to employ a research diver who is a trained marine biologist to assist in monitoring the impacts of dives on the marine environment as well as with informing the divers on ethical diving practices.

Safety and security

- Safety and security were aspects divers regarded as essential to their experience, which related to dive operators ensuring the safety of the divers at all times, being able to deal with emergencies and thorough safety briefings and checks. However, worryingly, while their expectations were met regarding safety and security at the dive destination, their expectations were not met by the dive operators. Safety briefings should be held by dive instructors before every dive so that the divers know what they must do in an emergency situation. Dive operators should furthermore guarantee that their dive instructors are well trained and certified by accredited diving organisations (PADI, SSI, etc.) so that they can deal with any emergencies that may arise. Dive operators should implement HIRA (Hazard Identification and Risk Assessment) developed by DANSA (South Africa), which is a protocol of hazard identification, risk assessment and emergency assistance/action plans at dive centres. The appointment of a DSO (Diving Safety Officer) who is trained in HIRA implementation, auditing and risk prevention can further assist in ensuring divers' safety and security.

Maintenance

- Divers expect well-maintained facilities as well as well-maintained gear and equipment. This implies that all the gear that is hireable by divers needs to be serviced on a six-monthly basis. This could also ensure the safety of divers. Regular maintenance of facilities is further required, for example showers, dressing rooms, and overall cleanliness.

Services, affordability and accessibility

- Delivering good quality service, being equipped for physically challenged divers, asking fair prices (value-for-money), ensuring uncrowded experiences (restricted number of divers at the dive site) and being easy to access/reach were another set of aspects that dissatisfied divers. The recommendations made previously with regard to these aspects should also be considered by dive operators to enrich the overall quality of the services they deliver. The aspect related to being equipped for physically challenged divers is, unfortunately, an aspect that cannot be easily addressed. In many instances, the setup and available infrastructure at dive destinations do not allow the necessary physical measures to be implemented to accommodate these divers. Dive operators should, however, consider encouraging

their instructors to become qualified to support physically challenged divers. Measures should also be taken to ease the transportation of physically challenged divers from the dive centre to the launching site.

🔊 Available amenities

- Divers had high expectations regarding the possibility of purchasing "Dive & Stay packages" (dive and accommodation) (at Portofino) as well as parking available at operators or at a discounted price that did not meet their requirements (globally as well as in Portofino). Again, the recommendation made regarding the integration of the offerings at the dive destination also applies here. This emphasises the need for dive operators and local business and service providers to work together in offering an enhanced diving experience.

While the afore-mentioned issues did not meet divers' expectations, the following aspects exceeded their expectations.

🔊 Credibility

- Dive operators being affiliated to a specific certification agency, their credible reputation, friendly and well-trained dive instructors and operators, and the strict enforcement of diving rules are essential qualities that divers regard as important when selecting an operator, but also when they evaluate their experience.

🔊 Integrated offerings available

- The following aspects were regarded as essential to a satisfactory experience: catering to different dive levels, being well marketed on various platforms, i.e. information is easily accessible, providing opportunities to hire equipment / gear, having flexible dive times (e.g. allowed to dive longer than scheduled), having a dive shop and/or equipment maintenance services available, offering full-days, offering other products and activities, being equipped for junior divers and having spacious charters.

The afore-mentioned critical aspects related to the dive operators as well as the aspects that divers regard as necessary at both the dive destination and site can easily be ensured with the implementation and adoption of a quality label.